

Digital Technology Skills for Employability and Global Competitiveness Required of Business Education Graduates from Delta State Tertiary Institutions

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13826242>

Abstract

The study focused on digital technology skills for employability and global competitiveness required of Business Education graduates from Delta State Tertiary Institutions. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey approach was employed for the study. 420 graduates of Business Education from Delta State tertiary institutions were used as the population of the study. The sample size of the study was 110 Business Education graduates from Delta State tertiary institutions using simple random sampling method. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by 3 experts in business education. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. The hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study shows that business education graduates highly require digital communication skills for employability and global competitiveness. Also, that there was no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on software and digital communication skills required for employability and global competitiveness. It was concluded that graduates of Business Education must possess strong digital communication abilities in order to be employable and competitive in the global market. It was, therefore, recommended among others that Business Education Lecturers should ensure that they effectively impact the knowledge of digital communication skills on their students while in school, because, it is highly required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Keywords: Digital Technology Skills, Employability, Global Competitiveness

Introduction

The entire world is shifting from the analog system to digital technological system. This is characterized by the digitalization of various sectors of the economy of the entire global system in the 21st century. Hence, digital technology skills is what business education graduates require at this moment for employability and global competitiveness. According to Okute et al. (2022) business education students need new skills sets which are known as digital skills to make them relevant after graduation. Acquisition of digital technology skills provide the proficiency to utilize digital devices, communication appliances and network to access and manage information. These skills include several competences that connect to technology, including software and appliances, digital tools and other computer hardware. These skills comprise a diversity of tasks employing digital literacy and methods of computing to complete relevant obligations for internal and

customer-facing activities. Industries make use of digital technology to manage sales, store and analyze customers' data and communicate relevant information. As industries continue to enlarge their use of online tools and digital technology to complete vital work procedures, workforces can benefit from understanding how to utilize these tools to communicate, manipulate and analyze relevant data.

On the other hand, digital skills are referred to as the ability to find, assess, utilize, share and create content using digital devices, such as smartphones and computers. According to UNESCO (2018) digital skills are a variety of skills to utilize digital gadgets, communication appliances, and networks to access and manage information. Cornell University in Burton (2016) in Kehinde and Olatunde (2022) defines digital skills as 'the ability to find, evaluate, utilize, share, and create content using information technologies and the Internet. While Chaouchi and Bourgeau (2020) upheld that some digital skills are required to use and interact with technology in order to fulfil specific tasks, while others are required to design, create and maintain tools and solutions for different industries. Conversely, the fast development of Internet access and connectivity has been ascribed to the growth of a digital economy around the world.

However, in today's world, the basic digital skills needed in the job settings are a little more sophisticated, and companies expect numerous employees to possess these skills rather than just a few persons. It has become obvious that technology is central to our lives, and as we become more dependent on digital communications and internet, employees must adapt to changing skill demands. Kehinde et al (2022) in their study upheld that digital communication skills is a basic necessity to reduce unemployment among business education graduates.

Apparently, the basic digital skills in today's world include online searching, email communication, virtual network management, cloud-based collaboration tools (for instance, Google Meet, Google Drive, Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Slack), document and spreadsheet creation, and basic device maintenance (e.g. updating software or activating an in-built device). Also, sharing a screen during video calls and managing team schedules using online calendars.

On the contrary, business education teaches students how to do business in a practical setting. As a result, business in the twenty-first century has taken on a new dimension, and the ability of a business school graduate to keep up with the evolving landscape is now crucial in the modern business environment. Consequently, graduates of business schools are expected to have proficiency with digital technologies, including office software and digital communication. Having these digital abilities will provide graduates of business education a competitive edge in the global market and allow them to be viewed as employable. For the business education students to acquire these skill, Timya (2022) established that lecturers required to a high extent digital technology skills for the teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions. However, Akpojotor (2022) affirmed that digitalization of business education will increase students' ICT abilities, intellectual and business competencies, and make them employable in the work force.

Employability is described as a multifaceted idea concerning an individual's ability to retain a self-rewarding work and human resource requirements for accomplishing operational responsibilities so as to function effectively in society (Oluwalola, 2019). The course Business education plays

an important role in employability skill acquisition by providing students with the necessary knowledge and skills to handle sophisticated office technologies and information systems required of all graduates for successful employment and to build them to be employable after graduation. Employability has emerged as an important quality for organizations to evaluate when hiring new staff. According to Akinbode et al. (2020), employability is the possession of pertinent information, abilities, and other characteristics by individuals that have facilitated the acquisition and maintenance of valuable employment. Ajisafe et al. (2015) asserted that business graduates' ability to get jobs is significantly influenced by their skills and competencies from their business education.

The authors theorized that business education holds the view of contributing to increase in job creation and self-employment of people. Consequently, a gainfully employed graduate will help to increase the Gross Domestic Product per capital of a nation of which business education help in providing employment or making the people to be self-employed. Also, Oliver (2015) describe employability as the ability to identify, obtain, acclimatize, and constantly enhance the skills, understandings and personal attributes that make graduates more liable to obtain and concoct meaningful paid or unpaid job that benefits themselves, the workforce, the local community, and the economy. Therefore, employability skills are those skills that an individual possessed before looking for or entering into a job as most jobs are globally competitive, business education graduates need to acquire employability skills that will make them to have a competitive advantage over other applicants.

Global competitiveness on the other hand is described as the teaching and receiving procedures that allow students to views issues, events, and opportunities, as well as a profuse knowledge of cultural diversity and languages to operate in different cultural backgrounds from the global perspective, with the aim of putting the students on same level with students from other parts of the globe (Ikpesu, 2017). According to Oko and Wagbara (2022) global competitiveness means the capacity of a goods or service to compete with their counterparts internationally. Thus, the curriculum for students is meant to help them learn, understand, and think internationally. Hence, global competitiveness is defined in this study as the acquisition of abilities that will allow business education graduates to compete favourably with graduates from the same field of study around the world.

However, this study focus on digital office software and digital communication skills as digital technology skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness

Consequently, employees of organizations can utilize digital office software to communicate competently and access their systems, tools and data that they require from any device or location. Since the 21st century work environment is ever-changing and dynamic, Kayii and Okiridu (2020) believed that soft skills which are non-academic, internalized, and emotional intelligence skills that are hard to measure are intra and interpersonal skills that are necessary for fostering relationships, enhancing distinguishability, and creating opportunities for advancement. Hence, graduates should possess these soft skills so as to be relevant to the labour market and to be considered for employment and also to be ever ready for global competitiveness. The graduates of

business education need to be acquitted with the e-signing software for signing documents on-line without necessarily printing of papers and to email the document to other signatory for signing without any linkage of information during this process. In other words, business education graduates should understand small pdf's e-signing, allowing them to sign their own documents, send them to others, track their progress, and send them in specific orders.

Online communication involves the use of emails, social media, blogs and websites to relate with other persons or businesses; and it therefore requires skills in these areas. Some essential skills here are content marketing, digital advertising, data-driven marketing, search engine optimization (SEO) and social media skills. it also include the ability to have a clear, concise, objective, consistent, complete, relevant, and understanding of audience knowledge; and share content information online using online platforms. Individuals who have the understanding of how to effectively utilize these technological abilities have advantage. As Doyle (2019) noted, employers across industries are looking for digital communication professionals with a variety of specific skill sets. These individuals are highly demanded for by organizations for everything from creating online brand assets to building an engaged social media audience with the hope of promoting sales and increase profits. Business education graduates considered in this study are basically males or females studying in public tertiary institutions. For Borgonovi et al., in Verkroost, et al. (2020) gender gaps disfavoring women in Internet access and basic digital skills can be sizeable, especially in developing countries, gender gaps in high-level digital skills, such as those required to work in jobs in the information technology (IT) sector, are thought to be even larger in most countries. Contrary to the above view, Kehinde et al. (2022) discovered in their study that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female graduates of business education on e-commerce related skills. Also, Ekoh-Nweke et al. (2022) found in their study that there was no significant difference in the mean scores of male and female business educators on the extent ICT skills strategy enhance teaching of business education in the new normal. On the basis of these findings, this study carried out an empirical study on digital technology skills for employability and global competitiveness required of business education graduates from Delta State tertiary institutions using gender as the moderating variable.

Statement of the Problem

The entire globe is changing continually as technology is changing from time to time steering up the need for new skills to meet up with the technological changes. In recent times, the business world has made some meaningful changes as a result of the COVID-19 Pandemic leading to workers working from home as a result of innovation in digital technology. It has been observed that it is very difficult for graduates to get jobs and fit into the digital economy of the 21st century without possessing the required digital skills as majority of graduates are found roaming the streets in search of jobs without possessing the required set skills for the changing economy.

Consequently the business education profession is not left out as graduates from this profession are required to possess certain digital skills to fit into the digital economy by employers of labour. These skills will make them to be employable and also enable them to compete globally with their counterparts from other parts of the world. This has become necessary as a substantial number of

deeds related to work, business, education, socializing and other activities have been enthused from the physical to the virtual sphere (Teltscher, 2020).

The need to determine whether the business education graduates possess these digital skills required for employability and global competitiveness prompted this study which is digital technology skills for employability and global competitiveness required of business education graduates from Delta State Tertiary Institutions

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to examine the digital technology skills for employability and global competitiveness required of business education graduates from Delta State Tertiary Institutions. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.
2. The digital communication skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness?
2. What are the digital communication skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses guided the study and were tested at 0.05 Alpha level:

1. There is no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.
2. There is no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on digital communication skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was employed for the study and it was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. A 30-item self-designed 4-point rating scale questionnaire titled: Digital Skills for Employability and Global Competitiveness Questionnaire (DSEGCQ) was used for data collection. Three experts from business education validated the instrument and to determine the reliability of the instrument, a Test-retest method was used and a pilot study conducted on 20 Business Education graduates from Edo State tertiary institutions and the reliability coefficient obtained was 0.76. The population of the study comprised 420 Business Education graduates of the 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 academic sessions from the Delta State tertiary institutions (College of Education, Warri, (138), College of Education, Mosogar, (59), Delta State University, Abraka,

(151) and University of Delta (formerly College of Education), Agbor, (72), (Source: Office of the Heads of Department). The sample of the study comprised of 110 Business Education graduates this was obtained through a simple random sampling technique. The researcher with the help of four research assistants one from each of the institutions administered the questionnaire on the respondents. This was made possible because most of the graduates are undergoing degree or post graduate programmes in the universities while others were reach through the tracer system that enable the researcher to reach out to the business education graduates through the help of the research assistant. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to analyze the data used in answering the research questions while the null hypotheses was tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significant. For any of the items in the research questions to be accepted as required, the individual item mean must not be less than 2.50, and so with the grand mean of each research question. Similarly, for any of the null hypotheses not to be rejected, the calculated P-value must be more than the critical P-value of 0.05 otherwise rejected.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What are the software skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the software skills required for employability and global competitiveness

S/N	Software Skills required for Employability and Global Competitiveness	X	SD	Remark
1	Ability to make use of Microsoft-word	3.65	0.76	Highly Required
2.	Ability to create and logically organized computer files and folders	3.08	0.60	Required
3.	Ability to use Web browsers (e.g., Mozilla Firefox, Microsoft Edge, Google Chrome, Opera)	3.43	0.68	Required
4.	Ability to use social media platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn)	3.46	0.54	Required

5.	Ability to create Microsoft-Excel document	3.75	0.86	Highly Required
6.	Ability to use Cloud storage services (e.g., Google Drive, iCloud, Dropbox)	3.30	0.75	Required
7.	Ability to use video conferencing software (e.g., Skype, Google Meet, Zoom)	3.15	0.67	Required
8.	Using digital camera, touch screen computer, trackballs for records creation.	2.75	0.88	Required
9.	Ability to make use of Microsoft- Access to produce management report	3.05	0.84	Required
10.	Multitasking with different application	3.20	0.67	Required
11.	Ability to use E-Commerce platforms (e.g., Amazon, eBay, Shopify)	3.35	0.79	Required
12.	Ability to use content management system (e.g., WordPress, Joomla, Drupal)	3.28	0.75	Required
13.	Proficiency of use of Cybersecurity and ethical hacking tools (e.g.,Kali Linux,Nmap, Burp Suite)	2.68	0.93	Required
14.	Capability to make use of Customer Relation Management Software(Salesforce, Hubspot)	3.45	0.56	Required
15.	Ability to generate a Power point work area	3.10	0.73	Required
16.	Ability to use Application/Software update	3.20	0.68	Required
17.	Ability to use Internet connection	3.50	0.83	Highly Required
Weighted average		3.26	0.74	Required

Table 1 above shows the responses of business education graduates on the software skills for employability and global competitiveness required. The result revealed that all the software skills items outlined were required for employability and global competitiveness with a weighted average/mean of 3.26 and standard deviation of 0.74. Items 1, 5 and 17 were however highly required with mean score of 3.65, 3.75 and 3.50 respectively. All the other items mean were between 2.65 to 3.46. All the 17 items in this scale have standard deviation scores ranging from 0.54 to 0.93. This indicates that the respondents were not wide spread in their responses as they are close to the mean. As this shows that all the software skills are required to be possessed by graduates of business education for employability and global competitiveness.

Research Question 2

What are the digital communication skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the digital communication skills required for employability and global competitiveness

S/N	Digital Communication Skills required for Employability and Global Competitiveness	X	SD	Remark
1.	Ability to make use of the internet application software (e.g. Google Chrome, Facebook, Google Drive, Microsoft Project etc.)	3.80	0.48	Highly Required

2.	Capacity to create and manage an e-mail account	3.60	0.64	Highly Required
3.	Effective use of visual aids and multimedia	3.65	0.72	Highly Required
4.	Google workspace	3.70	0.68	Highly Required
5.	Ability to download information from the internet	3.55	0.65	Highly Required
6.	Ability to upload information into the internet.	3.60	0.43	Highly Required
7.	Virtual conferencing skills	3.45	0.65	Required
8.	Ability to use search engines to get information	3.40	0.54	Required
9	Handling complex information in virtual networks	3.42	0.78	Required
10.	Use of cloud-based collaboration tools such as Google Meet, Google Drive, Zoom Microsoft Teams and Slack	3.55	0.66	Highly Required
11.	Producing and administering online documents and spreadsheets	3.60	0.76	Highly Required
12.	Sharing a screen while on a video conversation	3.30	0.87	Required
13	Effectively managing schedule and that of other members of the team through the use of online calendars	3.20	0.64	Required
	Weighted average	3.52	0.65	Highly Required

Table 2 above indicates the responses of Business Education graduates on the digital communication skills required for employability and global competitiveness. The result shows that all the digital communication skills items outlined were highly required with a weighted average mean of 3.52 and standard deviation of 0.65. items 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10 and 11 were however highly required with a mean score ranging from 3.55 to 3.80. The mean scores for all the items in the scale ranges from 3.20 to 3.80. This indicates that the respondents were not wide spread in their responses as they were close to the mean. This implies that digital communication skills are highly required by graduates of business education for employability and global competitiveness.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female business education graduates on digital software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of the variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness

Gender	N	x	SD	df	α	t-value	p-value	Decision
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Male	30	3.25	0.76						Not Significant
				108	0.05	1.42		0.54	
Female	80	3.32	0.92						

Table 3 shows that t-value 1.42 at 108 degree of freedom with a p-value of 0.54 is greater than the criterion value of 0.05(0.54 > 0.05). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This means that there is no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on software skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on digital communication skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Table 4: Summary of t-test of the variation of the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on digital communication skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness

Gender	N	x	SD	df	α	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	30	3.55	0.71					Not Significant
				108	0.05	0.98		0.34
Female	80	3.48	0.68					

Table 4 shows that t-value 0.98 at 108 degree of freedom with a p-value of 0.34 is greater than the threshold value of 0.05(0.34 > 0.05). Since p-value is greater than the significant value, the null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This indicates that there was no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on digital communication skills required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of research question one indicate that business education graduates require software skills for employability and global competitiveness. This is in agreement with the findings of Timya (2022) that lecturers required digital technology skills for teaching and learning business education courses in tertiary institutions to a high extent. Also, the finding of this study corroborates Akpojotor (2022) that digitalization of business education increase students’ ICT abilities, intellectual and business competencies, and make them employable in the work force Findings of the study on research question two revealed that digital communication skills are highly required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness. This finding corroborates the findings of Kehinde et al. (2022) that digital communication skills is a basic necessity to reduce unemployment among Business Education graduates.

The result of hypothesis one shows that there was no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on software skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness. This finding agrees with the findings of Kehinde et al. (2022) who discovered in their study that there was no significant difference in the mean score of male and female Business Education graduates on e-commerce related skills.

The result of hypothesis two indicates that there was no significant variation in the mean responses of male and female Business Education graduates on digital communication skills required by business education graduates for employability and global competitiveness. This result is in consonant with that of Ekoh-Nweke et al. (2022) who found that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators on the extent ICT skills strategy enhance teaching of Business Education in the new normal.

Conclusion

In accordance to the study's findings, it was concluded that graduates of Business Education must possess strong digital communication abilities in order to be employable and competitive in the global market. Also, that ability to make use of Microsoft-word, ability to create Microsoft-Excel document, and ability to use internet connection are highly required among others for business education graduates employability and global competitiveness.

Recommendations

In view of the afore-mentioned result of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The management of tertiary institutions and all stakeholders should ensure that they provide the necessary facilities and equipment required for training the Business Education students on software skills because in this 21st century the Business Education graduate need software skills to be able to gain employment and also to compete globally with their counterparts from other parts of the world.
2. Business Education Lecturers should ensure that they effectively impact the knowledge of digital communication skills on their students while in school, because, it is highly required by Business Education graduates for employability and global competitiveness.

References

- Ajisafe, E.O., Bolarinwa, K.O. & Edeh, T. (2015). Issues in business education programme: Challenges to National Transformation. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(21), 208-212
- Akinbode, J. & Oyelude, O. (2020). 21st century skills and fresh graduates' employability in Nigeria: The Human Resource Practitioners' Perspective. *Nigeria Journal of management studies*, 20(1), 172-179.
- Akpojotor, B.E. (2022). Digitalization of business education programme in tertiary institutions in Delta State, Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects. *ATBU Journal of Science Technology and Education (JOSTE)*, 10(2), 181-191
- Chaouch, H. & Bourgeau, T. (2020). *Will all jobs require programming skills in the growing digital society?* Retrieved from: <https://academy.itu.int/sites/default/files/media2/file/Digital%20Skills%20Insights%202020.pdf>

- Doyle, L. (2019). *What is digital communication and why are skilled professionals in such high demand?* Retrieved from <https://www.northeastern.edu/bachelors-completion/news/what-is-digital-communication/>
- Ekoh-Nweke, A.C., Ezeabii, I. C. & Ikpeama, F.U. (2022). Digital skills strategies for teaching business education in the new normal by educators in universities in South East Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education*, 9(1), 193-202
- Ikpesu, C. (2017). Globalizing business education curriculum experiences in Nigeria higher education for enhanced students' employability. *European Journal of Business and Innovation Research*. 5(5) 47-57
- Kayii, N.E. & Okiridu, O.S.F. (2020). Teachers' perception toward the integration of soft skills in teaching business students in secondary schools in Rivers State. *Vocational & Technology Education Journal (VOTEJ)*, 2(1), 39- 48.
- Kehinde, E. E. & Olatunde, A.M. (2022). Digital skills needed by business education graduates for unemployment reduction in the 21st century. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education*, 9(1), 134-148.
- Oko, M.C. & Wagbara, S.O. (2022). Digital skills needed by business education graduate for global competitiveness in entrepreneurship in Ebonyi State. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education*, 9(1), 225-230.
- Okute, A. L., Enang, C.E. & Etoma, M. G. (2022). Framework for digital skills acquisition for global competitiveness by business education students of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education*, 9(2), 172-182
- Oliver, B. (2015). Redefining graduate employability and work-integrated learning: Proposals for effective higher education in disrupted economies. *Journal of Teaching and Learning for Graduate Employability*, 6(1), 56-65.
- Oluwalola, F.K. (2019). Business studies and employability skills development in junior secondary schools in Ilorin Metropolis Kwara State. *eJournal of Education Policy*. Retrieved from: <http://nau.edu/COE/eJournal>
- Timya, N.N. (2022). Digital technology skills required for teaching and learning of business education courses in tertiary institutions in Plateau state. *Nigeria Journal of Business Education* 9(1), 158-168.
- UNESCO (2018). Digital skills critical for jobs and social inclusion. Retrieved from: <https://en.unesco.org/news/digital-skills-critical-jobs-and-social-inclusion>
- Verkroost, F.C.J., Kashyap, R., Garimella, K., Weber, I. & Zagheni, E. (2020). Tracking global gender gaps in information technology using online data. Retrieved from: <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:6cca777b-2521-4bc0-8f13-d1b6b6c50c1e>